

Government of Nepal

Ministry of Education, Science and Technology

MADAN BHANDARI

TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY

Development Board

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Message from Executive Director

Prof. Dr. Binod Aryal
Executive Director

"The holistic change of the society is a function of the Economic, Social, Cultural and Political awareness of the people" -**Hon. Madan Kumar Bhandari**

It is a matter of great pleasure for us to follow the Vision of Great leader Madan Bhandari for holistic change of society through technical education and community based program. One of the most important parts of our life is the prime of youth which is invested in Education. The investment always raises the expectations of returns during rest of life in multiple forms. I would like to say that technical education is the right field of study to be highly demanded resource. Nepal is in search of technical manpower more in number for sustainable transfer of the nation. Our national bureaucracy, defense, politics, and infrastructure and social sector -everywhere is an immense need of effective technician, experts and technical managers capable to respond with the effect of globalization. MBTU is not just a university but love, hope and believe for us to produce human capital for making Prosperous Nepal, Happy Nepali through poverty elavation with respect of skill.

It is believed that an educational institution is a place not only to gain knowledge but also to build character, enrich mind, and gain experiences that can last life time. The unity of interests and goals to integrate formal and informal learners together reflects the integrated spectrum of cultural diversity as a whole which makes their life easy. We are dedicated to fulfill the demand of society through the successful operation of MBTU with strong legal frame well equiped infrastructure and most important teaching and research activities. Kindly give your strong suport to overcome the educational demand of society by the creation of first technological university of Nepal.

We have already initiated the process of land acquisition and infrastructure development and draft of University Act has been submitted to line ministry. Curriculum is the backbone of the university which is under the process of development. Once again we humbly request you to give your intelletual's and physical support to us.

MBTU assures to provide Education, Environment and Experience for producing a Total Quality Human Resource who will be first choice of industry. I ensure to operate the university and invite you to join us for making history.

Our Voice

The clarion call of our government "Prosperous Nepal, Happy Nepalese" needs an action as our endeavors are still grossly insufficient in comparison with the volume of yield request. Development counts on how fast and effective way this will be made possible to the largest number of people in shortest possible time with most appropriate manner. Honorable Bhandari has stated "A worried person sees a problem, and a concerned person solves problem". Indeed, opportunities are latent and we, the problem solvers are dedicated to convert the challenges and crisis into opportunities. We need to develop human capital as root of all development activities. However, a large group of learners are not incorporated in main stream of education so far as they either miss at different levels or have been tried to be taught without considering their interest.

Changing technology, globalization, use of resources, climatic condition, aspirations of students, expectations of employers, desires of parents, obligations to the community etc. are forces operating to expect the unexpected. Each of these factors have multitude sub factors arising out of it, like changing technology leads to updated curriculum, alternative teaching methods, availability of time to devote for studies, affordability, variety of courses to be offered, availability of experts, students' choice etc. According to Michel Dell, 85% jobs for 2030 are not yet created, education and skill set have not yet been decided where as Fobes says 75% of the companies are going to disappear from the current space by 2025 and 50% of future companies are yet to be started. We are in VUCA world where our graduates should be hunter, not just planter or farmer. So, we need an independent academic institution which can assist to produce hunter by fusion of industrial need and technological advancement through its continuous research based curriculum for productive operation in the field of Agriculture, Natural Resources, Infrastructure (Airport, Railway), Manufacturing Industries, Construction, Mechatronics, Medical technology etc.

The hard work of 26 years has borne fruit as the Madan Bhandari Technological University at center level and Madan Bhandari Technological School at province level have been announced by the Government of Nepal to be operated from the upcoming session. The nation is peaking towards phenomenal growth and no better time could be available than this for all of us; including the final stakeholders i.e. students for learning diverse disciplines such as Medicine, Dentistry, Nursing, Engineering, Operations, Pharmacy, Para Medical Sciences, etc. I'm certain, that with proper guidance, motivation and experience of existing universities, this sparkling energy can be channelized and utilized. These institutions will indeed be the pioneers in the field of technological education and shall contribute to the socio-economic growth of our nation. We are confident that students seeking gainful employment and opportunities for entrepreneurship will be immensely benefited from MBTU.

We are sure that you will join with us to sustain our rich heritage and feel proud to produce and deliver qualitative and skilled human resource keeping in mind our social mission for creating history.

I humbly thank government of Nepal, MBTU promotional committee and all the hands of supporters

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Regards

MBTUDB

Introduction of University

Madan Bhandari Technological University (MBTU) is the national priority for the development and advancement of higher education, skill development, vocational education, Research and industrial advancement in Nepal. This also accelerates the enhancement of gross enrolment ratio in the technical higher education sector. The university will be operated as blue ocean competitive strategy as it targets for reaching the unreached through the innovative model of the University provides entry to all, enabling those from both the formal as well as informal systems to acquire education and skills with a view to provide education, training and skill development opportunities to the informal sector and unorganized workforce in order to build productivity also to provide vertical mobility to students undergoing technical, vocational and skill based education and training by offering Diploma, Bachelor, Master and Doctoral programs in high growth sectors and offer various specializations to prepare our youth towards gainful employment. The model has incorporated the strength and best practices of the vocational and skill development system followed in various countries as well as the characteristics of the national ethos and culture. It is to act as national skill Development Corporation of the nation based on industrial need applying action research and publish knowledge and solution through its own publication. It will provide learning, teaching, capacity, capability and skills development and research and development in higher and technical education, covering a wide spectrum of domains and specializations as may be relevant from time to time including, inter-alia, Engineering, Medical, Agricultural, Natural resources, industrial, Construction etc and their inter-disciplinary studies and development; for creating higher level of cognitive, affective and psychomotor (head, hearts and hands) abilities and higher levels of intellectual abilities; It aims to create and deploy new educational programs to promote creativity, innovation and entrepreneurship for inventing of new ways for development and social reconstruction and transformation by establishing the state-of-the-art facilities for education, vocational education, skill training and development through its professional and development services to the industry and public organizations and society. It acts as centers of excellence for research and development in Technology for socio-economic development, and for sharing knowledge and its application. It will use modern and post-modern processes, mechanisms and technologies for governance and management of learning, teaching, researching, evaluating, developing, organizing and creating socioeconomic wealth for individuals and society for the century. It always focus to start higher education programs, courses in new and emerging areas with innovative approaches by establishing links, collaborations and partnerships with other higher education and research institutions in Nepal and abroad. It will pursue any other objectives as may be suggested by the Government.

To provide learning opportunities to wide range of learners representing diverse backgrounds, age groups and socio-economic status and geographic location through a self-paced, self-styled learning environment; it will be operated in all 7 states gradually with specific focus at one location for excellency. Using concept of 'Virtual Campus' where students will come together with experienced faculty and industry members to develop, evolve and university will conduct regular research in labour market requirements in order to understand emerging trends and offer suitable curricula, courses and programs. Assuring council and university Grant Commission norms, it offers facility of credit banking or transfer system to create options of multi-entry and exit and opportunities, integrated degree, lateral entry

and dual degree for movement across Universities or domains or sectors. It will attempt to provide students an opportunity of life long and continuous training through University courses offered through conventional or blended or distance or open or online education and other education delivery models suitable for different pedagogical approaches and systems to trace and enhance performance. It should plan to establish Campuses, Skill Centers, Community Colleges, Study Centers, Information Centers, Test or Examination Centers, Centers of Excellence, Off Campus, Off shore Campuses, etc. at various locations in and outside the country to facilitate delivery, student services and dissemination of education, consultancy, information and skill training.

This university will be solution for developing sustainable economy focusing self-employment, employee in the nation overcoming high foreign deployment and it will also promote local technology and skills covering school drop outs at various levels.

Purposed Course

- Construction Technology
- Mechanical & Automation Engineering (Manufacturing Engineering/Control and instrumentation engineering/ Materials Engineering, Automation, operation)
- Mechatronics (mechanical, electrical, telecommunication, control and computer engineering)
- Rural Technology Development and Management
- Forestry and Wood Technology
- Agroforestry
- Agriculture Technology
- Livestock and Veterinary Technology
- Medical Technology (General, Radiotherapy, Medical Electronics)
- Clinical Technology (Clinical Research, Tissue Engineering, Animal Facility)
- Industrial Biotechnology
- Software Engineering
- Urban Development
- Mining and Metallurgy
- Dairy Technology
- Food Technology
- Nursing and Hospital Management.

Why MBTU ?

Technology has added manufacturing value resulting increase in per capita which could not make us competitive with only 1.5 % human capital growth rate in average. Based on educational statistics assessment of 2017, The total students who enroll in class 11/12 are 584072 including community school with 427268 and in private school 156786 students. Out of which only 239971 students at rate of 41% appear in the final examination of class 12 with a 49 % pass rate, 117778 students pass which around 20% only of enrollment. Similarly, for class 9/10, enrolment is 970720 pass out (34%)-330044 however 640676 cannot achieve successful educational objective. 466294 students struggled during 11/12 but cannot make the set target. In this way, only in 4 years of education 1106970 youth are losing which may cause the nation to be lost.

This is why it is urged to establish MBTU for including the excluded also with following attraction.

- Attempt to ensure access of all in Education through formalizing the informal skills.
- Vertical growth of skill based education through integration of Industry and Technology.
- Entry from Diploma, +2 and Informal sector after cognition test
- Cognition test will be conducted at each level.
- Entrepreneurship will be focused.
- Teaching with high industrial exposure
- Virtual campus for continuity of learning bringing industrial expert, academicians and researchers among students
- Social Entrepreneurship and incubation center for promotion of business applying action research of demand.
- Skill and knowledge with integrity and ethics
- Students incubation center under guidance of faculty
- Individual research center of faculty including students, industry expert and foreign faculty
- Central university to capture new demands
- Create uncontested market through first technological university.
- to waive courses and duration for the Diploma or similar relevant programs for experienced candidates (up to 1 or 2 semesters) - Lateral Entry
- of integrated master program in 5 years
- of dual degrees in different disciplines for fulfilling minimum requirements of individual program

Unique Course Specific Provisions

The infrastructure will be developed gradually in all states with head office and Engineering Technology at Kathmandu, Jagdol in the area of 3600 ropani and Study Excellence Center for forestry and Natural resource at Rayale, Kavare in the area of 1651 ropani of Bagmati Province together with Sustainable Himalayan technology operation at Lamachaur, Gandaki Province in the area of 3583 ropani and with same area at Belka, Udayapur of province 1 as excellence center for agriculture technology along with Medical Technology at Urlabari, Morang in the area of 267 ropani.

MBTU shall be different to other academic institutions in that it will integrate the knowledge of conventional technology of farmers, masons, foreman, blacksmith, goldsmith, carpenters and other native people with academic courses, in one side and on the other side; it will promote and upgrade the local technologies blending with modern technology. The research shall be carried out on the real ground. All these research shall be the applied research with solutions to prevailing issues. There will be MoUs with different industries, professional and industrial bodies for technology development, technology transfer, joint research projects and entrepreneurship development.

Vision: "Reaching the Unreached"

The vision of MBTU is to become the first technological university that produces Total Quality Human Capital, technologists and researchers competent and committed for building prosperous Nepal where citizens enjoy a life of greater security, well-being and personal dignity.

Mission: To offer technological, career-directed educational programs focusing on innovative problem-solving research in the field of engineering and technology, and allied sciences with a national identity and international outlook.

Objectives

Overall Objective: The overall objective of the university is to reach the unreached for the development and advancement of higher education, skill development, and vocational education in the country to "Prosperous Nepal, Happy Nepalese"

Specific Objectives:

- To offer competitive technological education with sound theoretical knowledge and practical foundations for producing human capital to meet the needs of society and national development plans,
- To engage in research and development activities to explore meaningful and useful technology to improve productivity and income of enterprises,
- To provide carrier pathways for the graduates of technical and vocational education.
- To minimize the gap of academic knowledge and knowledge at workplace.
- To provide professional and development services to the industry, organizations, agencies and the society at large;
- To upgrade the conventional knowledge and skill prevailing in the workplace to the level of present-day technology through certification and innovation.
- To strengthen the teaching and research on problem-based approach and integrate academic knowledge to production areas, so that the productivity could be enhanced and aspirations of the consumers could be fulfilled.
- To provide Highly qualified and motivated faculties, staffs, competent students, modern infrastructure, new academic programs, research laboratories, innovation and creativity workshops, and other education resources shall be the integral components of the university.
- To assure national development through Technological innovation, employment and wealth creation, improvement of living standards of the people and creation of self-employment opportunities in the country. This will help improve productivity and economy of the nation.
- To collaborate and cooperate between industry and academia for overcoming the issue of employment opportunity of fresh graduates through an exposure to current practices in the industry. Experts from industry shall be appointed as adjunct faculty members and as examiners for students' project evaluation.

Development Board Staff

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Office Helper

Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra
Expert

National Qualifications Framework (NQF) Nepal- Main Frame

Approved by the Cabinet on 03-May, 2020

TVET: Technical and Vocational Education and Training, (+): Indicates additional technological and Practical Components as required for each level of NVQF, QA: Qualification Accessed as per the set criteria by National Qualifications Authority (NQA), GE: General Education, RPL Recognition of Prior Learning. ISCED: International Standard Classification of Education

The minimum training, education and skill for award of the degree would be maintained as per National Qualification Framework (NQF) approved by Government of Nepal.

Global mobility of skilled workforce from Nepal, through international equivalence of National Qualification framework (NQF) would be made consistent with the practice of required country by adding technological and practical components as required for equivalency for assuring international acceptance.

Mobility between vocational and general education would create and opportunity for institution to attract high scoring students.

Vertical growth of skill based education through integration of industry and technology would be helpful to overcome unemployment and poverty.

Modified National Skill Qualification Framework of SAARC

NSQF Level ~4	Certificate (06 Months-30 Credits after 10 + 12)
NSQF Level~5	Diploma (01 Year-60 Commulative Credits after 10 +2)
NSQF Level~6	Advanced Diploma (02 Years-120 Commulative Credits)
NSQF Level~7	B.Tech. Degree (03 Years -180 Cumulative Credit after 10 +2)
NSQF Level~8	P.G. Diploma (01 Years -60 Credits after B. Tech.)
NSQF Level~9	M.Tech. Degree (02 Years -120 Credits after B. Tech.)
NSQF Level~10	Research Level (Minimum Standards and Procedure for Award of PH.D or D.Sc.Degrees)

Most of the Nation has developed a framework for following outcomes including India:

- Mobility between vocational and general education by alignment of degrees with NSQF
- Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL), allowing transition from non-formal to organized job market
- Standardized, consistent, nationally acceptable outcomes of training across the country through a national quality assurance framework
- Global mobility of skilled workforce from India, through international equivalence of NSQF.
- Generating respect for workers.
- Creating entrepreneur and innovative work force for National Development.
- Overcome the issue of the poverty gradually through succession of attitude and knowledge based skill human capital.

Welcome to Join your hands with us for establishing first Technological University of Nepal. With your love, hope and believes, we assure total quality people for National Development.

Madan Bhandari Technological University (MBTU)

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